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**TANG VA SUN SULOLASI DAVRIDA
MUSULMONLARNI TINCHLANTIRISH VA YUMSHATISH SIYOSATI**

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ketma-ket kelgan feodal tuzumlar islom dinini boshqarishga katta ahamiyat berib, bir qator siyosatlar ishlab chiqdilarki, ularni quyidagicha umumlashtirish mumkin: musulmonlar qalbi va ongini yumshatish; ularni o'rgatish uchun konfutsiylikni eksport qilish. Bu jamiyat muvozanatiga va islomning takomillashuviga samarali ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar: Xitoy feodal rejimi; siyosat; musulmonlar; Islom; evolyutsiya; Tang imperatori Taizong, Tyan-Shan tog'lari.

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**ПОЛИТИКА УМИРОТВОРЕНИЯ И СМЯГЧЕНИЯ МУСУЛЬМАН ПРИ
ДИНАСТИЯХ ТАН И СУН**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Сменявшие друг друга феодальные режимы придавали исключительную важность управлению исламом и формулировали набор политик, которые можно резюмировать следующим образом: смягчить сердца и умы мусульман; экспортировать конфуцианство, чтобы учить их. Это оказало эффективное влияние на баланс общества и улучшение ислама.

Ключевые слова: китайский феодальный режим; политика; мусульмане; Ислам; эволюция; император Тан Тайцзун, горы Тянь-Шань.

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THE POLICY OF PACIFYING AND SOFTENING MUSLIMS DURING THE TANG AND SONG DYNASTIES

ABSTRACT

Successive feudal regimes connected exquisite significance to the administration of Islam and formulated a collection of policies, which have been summarized as follows: to soften the hearts and minds of the Muslims; to export Confucianism to teach them. These had an effective impact on the balance of society and the improvement of Islam.

Index Terms: Chinese feudal regime; Policy; Muslims; Islam; Evolution; Emperor Tang Taizong, Tianshan Mountains.

Introduction: During the height of the Tang Dynasty (618–907) in China, Islam first appeared on the Arabian Peninsula in the seventh century AD. Othman, the third Caliph of the Arabian state, sent his first emissary to China in 651 A.D. (the second year of the Tang dynasty's Yong Hui period), and more and more Muslim traders, envoys, travelers, and craftsmen from Arabia, Persia, and Central Asia arrived in China via the Silk Road and the Spice Route to conduct business. From the Tang to the Qing dynasties, as the Muslim population grew and its impact on Chinese politics, the economy, society, and culture changed, various Islamic policies were developed and put into practice in accordance with local circumstances and governing objectives, and these policies had various effects on the Muslim population. Using a historical sociology perspective, this study aims to investigate the causal and beneficial connections between regime policies and certain social groups or communities.

Literature review: This article uses the scientific research of the following scholars: Bai Shouyi's "General History of China" (Vol. 6) and "The History of the Hui-Hui People in China", Wang Jiainan's "The History of Cultural Exchange between China and Foreign Countries", and Yu Zhengui's articles from "The Chinese Regimes and Islam". These articles contain the necessary information on the subject.

Research Methodology: The cause-and-effect relationship examines the motivations behind the regime's actions and how they affect the Muslim population, or the Islamic community. Contrarily, constructive relations examine how individuals perceive the interdependence, mutual influence, and causality between the regime and the community, as well as how these perceptions and findings affect the policy in the opposite way. The motive for the usage of coverage as an entry factor for this lesson is that coverage is an outward act of the state, and any coverage is made on the premise of political stability, in the context of cultural interests, based totally on financial needs, and guided by social order. Policy is the state's outwardly discernible action. Every decision on a policy is founded on the principles of political stability, cultural interests, economic necessities, and social order. The intention and driving force behind each policy are the state power's perception of and attitude toward the subject matter as well as its desire to advance the subject matter in the desired direction, i.e., to realize specific societal objectives.

It should be noted that the national situation or comprehensive national strength here does not refer to the real state of the country in a completely objective way, but to the perception and evaluation of the country's position in the internal and external environment through a series of comprehensive analysis and judgment, and the psychological feelings arising from such perception and evaluation. Such perceptions and judgments may not be completely objective and correct, and sometimes they may be misperceptions, misjudgments, or even fabrications, which are inevitably mixed with many subjective and contingent factors. This paper focuses on the perception of identity between the regime and the Muslim community.

Analysis and results: The governments of the Tang and Song dynasties primarily followed the "beneficence and pacification" and "wilful tie-up" policies towards Islam and Muslims. Muslims were treated with tolerance and acceptance by the ruling class. In essence, both sides saw each other as "friends" and "partners" who could work together in trade and cultural exchange to coexist happily.

In Chinese history, the Tang Dynasty was a time of unification, power, and prosperity. The society was politically stable and economically developed during this time, and the ethnic policy of

"beneficence and conciliation" earned Emperor Tang Taizong the title of "Heavenly Khan" from the emissaries of all ethnic groups[1,P.1276]. Tang Taizong also rose to become the common master of all ethnic groups. Chang'an and Liangzhou, which became the center of cross-cultural convergence, drew all kinds of scientific, artistic, and religious ideas due to their welcoming social and cultural environments. Through the mixing and fusion of Chinese and foreign civilizations, the Tang culture was able to develop new aspects thanks to the open and liberal social environment.

In his interactions with envoys and people, the monarch totally perceived the financial prosperity, countrywide strength, cultural power, and status of the ruler. The mentality of a fantastic energy provides for the magnanimity and tolerance of the regime, which consciously and unconsciously blanketed the picture and status of the nation as a crucial section of the countrywide pastime and smooth strength of the country. "The Tang, on the other hand, viewed its status in the West as a supreme honor"[2,p.137]. It was feasible to create a patronizing and tolerant ethnic policy thanks to a great-power attitude that exuded extreme confidence. "The barbarians are also human beings whose feelings are not different from those of China and Xia," according to Tang Emperor Taizong. The ruler of the people is a man of virtue, so there is no need for them to be wary of visitors. Cover the virtue, and ze Qi is four barbarians who can create such a family; suspicion is more flesh and blood and is unavoidably an adversary[3,p.1278]. In order to ensure the smooth flow of the Northwest Silk Road, the Tang Dynasty set up post houses along all the thoroughfares from Liangzhou in the Hexi Corridor to the northwest of the Tianshan Mountains to provide food, lodging, and forage for the merchants and stationed troops along the road to protect them[4,p.143]. This extraordinarily assured outstanding energy mentality used to be specifically normal of the way in which envoys have been treated: the fee of the emperor's rewards used to be a good deal greater than the fee of the tributes paid by means of the emissaries, and some retailers even posed as envoys for this cause due to the fact their "tribute" may want to frequently be repaid numerous instances over from the court.

An inclusive cultural coverage assumes that cultural variety and pluralism have been diagnosed and that exceptional people should come to be equal "friends". Thus, it was once not solely the financial advantages but also the open social surroundings and inclusive cultural environment of the Tang Dynasty that attracted Arab, Persian, and Central Asian Muslim retailers from far and wide. This environment and ecosystem no longer solely attracted a giant range of Muslim retailers, but additionally gave a fine impetus to the introduction of Islam into China.

If the Islamic coverage of the Tang Dynasty mirrored the inclusive mentality of sturdy tradition, extra pursuing the pleasure of countrywide picture and prestige, then the Islamic coverage of Song Dynasty mof therored an extra sensible mindset, pursuing utilitarianism. The core of the Song Dynasty's coverage of "tying up with Islam and Muslims" used to be to reflect on realistic monetary interests. Because of the Song regime, distant places were once a vital lifeline of its monetary life. In order to increase the seafaring trade, the courtroom dispatched eight chamberlains with presents to the Hainan provinces in the fourth year of Emperor Taizong Yongxi (987). Moreover, successive regimes of the Song dynasty stimulated effective households to construct sea vessels to buy items to function in foreign places as personal merchants. It was once additionally stipulated that all country-wide captains who have been able to "recruit and entice shipments" and overseas sea retailers who have been energetic in transporting items had been "compensated with reliable differences"; all and sundry who "lost the expenses of items to the overseas merchants" and affected the seafaring change used to be punished by means of demotion[5, p. 206]. The Song dynasty ended the feudalism of the Five Dynasties and Ten Kingdoms, and a new technology of peace emerged after the Tang dynasty. At the same time, the kingdom of Great Food used to be under the technology of the Abbasid dynasty, and after controlling the maritime hegemony west of the Indian Ocean, the kingdom of Great Food persevered to reinforce maritime visitors and interacted with the Song dynasty extra and extra frequently. Many of the exquisite meal retailers posed as messengers to pay tribute to China for two reasons: firstly, the courtroom observed the customs of the Tang dynasty to supply beneficiaries, and the tributes had been entertained through neighborhood officers along the way; secondly, the tributed items had been exempted from industrial taxes along the way[6, p. 269].

The distant places of the Song Dynasty were once usually divided into two forms: "tribute trade" and "market trade". The nation adopted the coverage of "pass its public choices and levy its personal goods" for trade in remote places: no tax ought to be levied on tribute merchandise as referred to before, but tax had to be amassed on market-port trade. The tax income of the market change should attain one twentieth of the state's revenue, which suggests its contribution to the economic system of the Song Dynasty[7,p.53], and the vital role of Muslim merchants in the distant places change can be seen.

In fact, throughout the Tang and Song dynasties, the Muslim purchasers were once small in number and generally engaged in industrial change things to do with a fantastically confined circle of expatriates. For example, in the course of the Tang Dynasty, Muslim monks have been a tremendous financial force in port cities such as Guangzhou and Yangzhou and had some impact on neighborhood socioeconomic and cultural life; however, they usually no longer had an actual influence on the economy, politics, and subculture of mainstream society. Therefore, beneath the coaching of Tang Emperor Taizong's countrywide view that "the four barbarians should be made to be like one family," the Tang regime no longer[8, p. 270]. The Song Dynasty Muslims grew in variety and influence and grew to be a new group; however, their social activities and the Islam they practiced were nevertheless limited to the Muslim merchant circle and did not come into direct conflict with common Chinese culture.

The Tang and Song dynasties handled Muslims in their territories as "friends": politically, they gave them truthful and equal possibilities for promotion and corresponding treatment and even opened up the imperial examinations to them, permitting them to enter the civil service; economically, the Song regime inspired Muslim retailers to enlarge their enterprise and pay greater taxes. In monetary terms, the Song regime inspired Muslim retailers to amplify their business, pay greater taxes, and confer reliable positions on those who actively paid tribute and had been enthusiastic about trade. public cemeteries, etc[9,p.27]. With the permission of the Song government, many mosques have been constructed in Chinese cities where Muslims lived, and those that continue to exist today consist of the Huaisheng Temple in Guangzhou, the Shengyou Temple in Quanzhou, the Xianhe Temple in Yangzhou, and the Niujie Mosque in Beijing.

Conclusion: The Muslims of the Tang and Song dynasties essentially lived in concord with the Chinese and different ethnic minorities in China due to an extra-cosy religious and ethnic policy. After the Southern Song Dynasty, the wide variety of Muslims dwelling in the southern section of the United States multiplied as the political middle shifted southward, and the variety of Muslims who married and married neighborhood residents increased, and their descendants grew to become the ancestors of the Muslims from the expatriate neighborhood to the Muslim community.

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